

The Future of the History of Capitalism¹:

The Time-Space Continuum of History and Development in the Story of Capitalism

Draft

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Introduction

In physics, the settled consensus around the Newtonian laws that had dominated the field for centuries was upended by the discovery of the time-space continuum. The implications of this for the discipline was the replacement of a model that yielded artificial certainty, by one that, by acknowledging greater complexity, was much better poised to grapple with the intricacies of physical reality. By analogy, I will argue in this paper, that the combine of emergent empirical insights into the nature of global capitalism calls for a similar paradigm shift in how we theorize it—and, indeed, mainstream economics itself.

The story of global capitalism—as told by much of mainstream economics, in the vein of Newtonian physics—is a seductively, if somewhat deceptively, simple one. Two crucially important empirical dimensions are, however, conspicuous by their absence in the orthodox economics scholarship—the “then” of history and the “now” of development. The perspective provided from these vantage points illustrates that far from the frictionless account of mainstream economics—populated by what Ostrom called “institution-free institutions”²—the history of the evolution of global capitalism in the global North and its transplantation to the global South both attest to it as a fraught process of continual contestation, with the State as the protagonist at the very heart of the drama. In both instances, the dynamics of relations between market, State, and indeed society, have been the product of active political choice rather than passive mechanical movements—and it is these choices that have shaped the institutional trajectory of global capitalism. I will also make the argument that the current political moment—when the fractures in both the explanatory, and predictive, capacities of theoretical accounts of global capitalism are starting to become increasingly evident—is rife for the, as yet

¹The title of this paper is borrowed from an essay I published last year, A. Haldar (2018), “The Future of the History of Capitalism” in *The Independent*, May 18 (https://www.independent.co.uk/news/long_reads/capitalism-future-east-west-uncontrollable-a8351311.html).

²E. Ostrom (1990), *Governing the Commons*, Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, p. 267.

underappreciated, alliance between the history of capitalism and development scholarship to make a collective bid to more fundamentally reshape the theory of global capitalism.

In this brief paper, I will lay out my argument in five parts. In the first, I will describe the mythologized account of the development of capitalism in the global North as per the economics orthodoxy. In the following section, I will provide a view of what this process looked like from a historical perspective, relying mainly on the history of capitalism literature. In the next section, I will provide an account of what the unfolding story of global capitalism looks like from the point of view of development theory, largely in the global South. In the penultimate section, I will make the argument that the epistemic elitism of the theory of capitalism—that extrapolates a universal model based on the experience of WEIRD (Western, educated, industrialized, rich and democratic) societies³ over a limited time period—greatly impoverishes our understanding of the phenomenon of capitalism more broadly. In the final section, I will offer some summary conclusions and make the case for what has the potential to be a rich future collaborative research agenda.

The overall argument I make is: whether global capitalism, that predominates over much of the world today, is seen as the inevitable product of autonomous forces *or* the result of, at least partially conscious, choices of actors (individuals, groups, States, firms, international organizations and so on) within the matrix of a highly complex labyrinth – also of our own making – is of great salience, especially with regard to the susceptibility of the resulting arrangements to moral evaluation and our collective sense of their mutability.

The Abbreviated Economic History of the Global North

As per the dominant paradigm in mainstream economics—neoclassicism—the evolution of the market economy is simply the product of mechanical parts interacting in a frictionless ecosystem,⁴ and the evolution of global capitalism merely an extension of the Ricardian logic of “comparative advantage”.

³ The term was coined by a group of University of British Columbia-based behavioral scientists and first articulated in J. Henrich, S.J. Heine and A. Norenzayan (2010), “The Weirdest People in the World?”, *Behavioral and Brain Sciences* 33, p. 61-135.

⁴ See, for a reflective account on the oversimplifications of the neoclassical paradigm, S. Bowles and W. Carlin (2019), “What Students Learn in Economics 101: Time for a Change”, *Journal of Economic Education* (forthcoming).

Under the assumptions of neoclassical economics, the mythology of the market is as a place where information is complete and verifiable, competition is perfect, the only existing evaluative criterion for the economy is Pareto-efficiency (i.e., the fullest exploitation of gains from trade or exchange) and the system largely self-stabilizing. Even more bizarre than the framing conditions are the actors that populate the economy—the far-sighted, endlessly materialistic and selfish *homo economicus* of rational choice theory⁵—interacting in a social space defined purely by buying and selling in the context of the market. These transactions are inured by contracts that are complete and enforceable at no cost in a regime where private property is the most important of institutions. Fundamental determinants of the physical constraints on the economy—both nature and technology—are external to the models, as is any account of power or agent heterogeneity, and, so, the extraction of economic rents.

The State, in this account, is reduced to the role of a Marshall-Pigou style auctioneer. Its identity exfoliated of all the scars of genealogy—slavery, colonialism or genocide. Indeed, within the narrative of neoclassical economics, markets are more efficient at solving almost all allocative problems subject to operating within an institutional frame where the State provides enforceable contracts and the protection of private property. This position was most strenuously defended by the highly influential Chicago School of Law and Economics that posited that the allocation and protection of property right was all but a necessary and sufficient condition for economic growth⁶, but has also been defended by the relatively more nuanced school of New Institutional Economics that traces the basis of the growth of nations to the possession of conducive institutional structures, typically narrowly interpreted to emphasize property rights⁷. This thesis has also been reiterated by more recent scholarship on “legal origins”⁸ and “why nations fail”⁹. The market economy of global capitalism is—in this portrayal—the product of what Hayek would refer to as a spontaneous order, independent of historical trajectory or political choice.¹⁰ It is also invulnerable to moral assessment.

Indeed, it is the unique parlor trick of neoclassical economics—shaking off war-era ideological acrimony—to scrub the subject of anything with a hint of normativity (politics, values etc.). Its

⁵ See further on this, A. Haldar (2018), “Intrinsic Goodness” in the *Times Literary Supplement*, October 30 (<https://www.the-tls.co.uk/articles/private/intrinsic-goodness/>).

⁶ R. Coase (1988): *The Firm, the Market and Law*, Chicago: Chicago University Press is considered the seminal text.

⁷ D. North (1990): *Institutions, Institutional Change and Economic Performance*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.

⁸ R. La Porta, F. Lopez-de-Silanes, A. Shleifer R.W. and Vishny (1998): “Law and Finance” *Journal of Political Economy* Vol. 106.

⁹ D. Acemoglu, S. Johnson, J.A. Robinson (2002): “Reversal of Fortune: Geography and Institutions in the Making of the Modern World Income Distribution”, *Quarterly Journal of Economics* 117.

¹⁰ See, for example, F. A. Hayek (1944): *The Road to Serfdom*, London, Routledge.

methodological weapon in making the claim to complete normative neutrality is the deployment of quantitative precision unprecedented in the social sciences. Imbued with the hubris of becoming a *pure science*, post-war neoclassical economics purported to devise a reliable, universally-applicable maximizing equation for society—largely irrespective of any contextual or, until recently, even cognitive considerations¹¹. It presumed, in the main, to be limitless in its capacity to turn boundless individual rationality into endless material wellbeing, to cull out of infinite resources (on a global scale) indefinite global growth—and, in so doing, to definitively replace faltering human touch with the infallible “invisible hand” and discourses of exploitation with those of merit.

This stylized account – largely the product of physics envy-based epistemic shifts in the intellectual history of economics that decontextualized the discipline – became also a kind of potted history of the evolution of capitalism in the West or the global North and congealed into a rigid theoretical orthodoxy. Cases that were aberrations from the paradigm were not dealt with robustly by the mainstream by dint of being from “Somewhere Else” (variously, the East or the global South) or “Another Time” (History). This theoretical “othering”—both spatially and temporally—became a standard, and dangerous, move in much of economic theory, particularly to the extent that these conjectures became the basis for the key prescriptions of the international economic order.

Then: Excavating the Origins of Capitalism

In stark contrast with the artificially-tidy account of the story of global capitalism within the mainstream economics perspective, the work of historians like Beckert in the *Empire of Cotton*¹² – and the burgeoning literature on the history of capitalism – is contributing to the development of a vocabulary that can provide a more textured account of its global history. As Beckert comments:

“Too often, we prefer to erase the realities...from the history of capitalism, craving a nobler, cleaner capitalism...Capitalism was in many ways a liberating force, the foundation of much of contemporary life; we are invested in it, not just

¹¹ See, on the continued resistance of mainstream neoclassical economics to incorporating even relatively conservative insights from the behavioral revolution, A. Haldar (2018), “Economics: The Discipline that Refuses to Change” in *The Atlantic*, December 14 (<https://www.theatlantic.com/education/archive/2018/12/why-do-econ-classes-barely-mention-behavioral-economics/578092/>) .

¹² S. Beckert (2014): *Empire of Cotton: A Global History*, New York, Knopf.

economically but emotionally and ideologically. Uncomfortable truths are sometimes easier to ignore.”¹³

This temptation to eulogize the economic system that is so core to Western society risks turning the discourse around capitalism into one of aspiration or even belief rather than the subject matter of scientific study. In particular, there are two “uncomfortable truths” that Beckert’s work underscores. The first is to do with the intertwined fates of capitalists and States. As Beckert puts it:

“capitalists and states arose hand in hand, each facilitating the ascendancy of the other...historically, capitalists’ greatest source of strength was their ability to rely on unusually powerful states—and simultaneously, for much of capitalism’s history, the greatest weakness of these same capitalists was that dependence on the state.”¹⁴

The second is to do with the human *costs* that greater fidelity to engaging with the history of capitalism forces us to confront. As Beckert points out, “Slavery, colonialism, and forced labor, among other forms of violence, were not aberrations in the history of capitalism, but were at its very core.”¹⁵

It is confronting precisely this Janus-headed quality of global capitalism—as, at once, the source of our current material prosperity and moral revolutions¹⁶ *and* as the fount of brutality and inequality on an unprecedented scale—that a new theory of it will have to contend with. But grappling with its fraught origins will better equip us to do this than showing fidelity to the roster of unsubstantiated founding myths that has, so far, defined the discourse. As Beckert describes the institutional origins of capitalism:

“We associate industrial capitalism with contracts and markets, but early capitalism was based as often as not on violence and bodily coercion. Modern capitalism privileges property rights, but this earlier moment was characterized just as much by massive expropriations as by secure ownership. Latter-day capitalism rests upon the rule of law and powerful institutions backed by the state, but capitalism’s early phase, although ultimately requiring state power to create world-spanning empires, was frequently based on the unrestrained actions of

¹³ *Ibid* p. xviii

¹⁴ *Ibid* p. 440

¹⁵ *Ibid* p. 441

¹⁶ For an exhaustive roster of the triumphs of human progress, largely enabled to capitalism see S. Pinker (2018), *Enlightenment Now*, London, Penguin.

private individuals—the domination of masters over slaves and of frontier capitalists over indigenous inhabitants.”¹⁷

The approach taken by the history of capitalism literature in shining a bright light on the detail of the dynamics by which the institutions of capitalism evolve is markedly different from most recent scholarship in economic history—including the seminal work of North and Weingast¹⁸—that treats institutions alongside its traditional fetishes (e.g., geography), as a key, if exogenous or extrinsic, determinant of economic growth.

This more complex picture is starting to be incorporated into the rubric of mainstream economics. Historians working within economics, like Chang¹⁹ and Piketty²⁰, are increasingly questioning the validity (especially in the light of empirical evidence) of the received wisdom on both the *emergence* (i.e., as a more or less autonomous process) and the *effects* (i.e., as eventually “trickling down”) of Western capitalism. Chang’s *Kicking Away the Ladder* has long made the case that the West may be misremembering the trajectory of its own ascent to power, establishing that the State was, in fact, front and center in charting the course of the global North even if its role was subsequently obscured from the narrative. Piketty’s *Capital* decisively shows that the hypothesis of the famed Kuznets curve (i.e., that inequality will initially rise in the wake of economic growth but eventually fall) is far from inevitable given rates of return in capital and labor markets. The influence of Piketty’s thesis illustrates the potential salience of history in shaping the narrative of mainstream economics that treated inequality as a vestige of class-based feudalism. Contrary to the notion that inequality in a capitalist system is self-correcting, Piketty’s evidence shows that apart from a brief period of turmoil around the World Wars (involving, in addition to several tectonic shifts at the global level, significant governmental intervention) industrial capitalism and persistent inequality have proven remarkably compatible. The burgeoning political—and academic—concern with inequality in the current scenario attests to this.

Instead of the one-dimensional portrayals of capitalism standard in economic theory, we are forced to conclude with Beckert that “civilization and barbarity are linked at the hip”.²¹ It is only,

¹⁷ *Ibid* p. xvi

¹⁸ See, for instance, D. North and B.R. Weingast (1989), “Constitutions and Commitment: The Evolution of Institutions Governing Public Choice in Seventeenth Century England” in *Journal of Economic History*, Vol. 49, Issue 4, p. 803-32.

¹⁹ H.J. Chang (2005): *Kicking Away the Ladder*, London: Anthem Press.

²⁰ T. Piketty (2014): *Capital in the Twenty-First Century*, Cambridge: Belknap Press.

²¹ *Ibid* p. 442.

however, by taking a forensic approach to studying the origins of capitalism—and, equally, its functioning in different settings—that we can start to develop an account of how the more emancipatory of the two forces can be made to trump the less.

Now: Capitalism Under Construction

If the history of capitalism literature excavates the archeological origins of capitalism, as it were, most parts of the global South and the “transition economies” can be seen, by analogy, as current construction sites for global capitalism: all the moving parts of the system still visible through the scaffolding. To the extent that these regions have negotiated the transition to capitalism in living memory, or, indeed, are doing so now, they have the potential to act as a type of petri-dish for experiments in the construction of capitalism and for testing the veracity of theories on the functioning of institutions.

The problem, however, has been that instead of seeing developing nations as crucibles for supplying living, breathing data for empirically testing theory, the approach has been to unquestioningly apply the formula derived from the orthodox scholarship—euphemistically referred to as a package of “reforms”. On the basis of its “narratives from the North” on the evolution of capitalism, the distillate of wisdom that was conveyed to the non-Western world crystallized into a rigid system of “one-size-fits-all” institutional prescriptions that were deemed essential prerequisites for economic growth, broadly known as the Washington Consensus policy package. In the case of the global South, it took the shape of World Bank and International Monetary Fund loan conditionalities and structural adjustment²², while in the post-Communist transition economies and in a few other instances, this took the form of what came to be popularly referred to as “shock therapy”²³ (loosely inspired by the economic transition of West Germany in 1948). These came to be collectively known in the literature as “big bang” approaches. More recently, the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI)²⁴ and the Doing

²² For an account based on a ringside view of the application of these reform packages particularly in the developing world context, see J. Stiglitz (2002) *Globalization and Its Discontents*, London: Penguin.

²³ This broad package of policies was applied in Chile in 1975, Bolivia in 1985 and in various post-Communist States thereafter, perhaps most notably Poland.

²⁴ This looks at six dimensions of governance: voice and accountability, political stability and absence of violence, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, rule of law and control of corruption, see <https://info.worldbank.org/governance/wgi/>.

Business Indicators²⁵ have made attempts at quantifying the quality of the “business environment” or “investment climate” along similar lines.

There are clear paradigms of progress that underlie these various policy prescriptions and indicators: fiscal discipline (and the avoidance of large deficits) is paramount, public subsidies are suspect, taxes need to be kept modest, interest rates should be market determined, exchange rates should be competitive, trade liberalization or the opening up of economies is to be emphasized, Foreign Direct Investment is to be attracted at virtually any cost and State enterprises are to be privatized post-haste. The unifying ideas are that less regulation is better than more, private is better than public, the “rule of law”—reduced to the protection of private property and the enforcement of contracts—is key for growth and “ease of doing business” or a “pro-business” approach is all-important.

As the “Doing Business 2020—Sustaining the Pace of Reforms” report states²⁶:

“...inefficient or inadequate regulation can stifle entrepreneurial activity and business growth and impact the ease of doing business. It takes over 200 hours to complete export border requirements for maritime transport in Cameroon and Côte d’Ivoire. In contrast, it takes only 10 hours in Singapore. Border compliance costs for export at seaports in Gabon average over \$1,600, but just over \$300 in Mauritius...Burdensome rules may drive businesses away from the oversight of regulators and tax collectors into the shadows of the informal sector or out of the country in search of a more supportive business environment. Foreign investors may shun economies where rules prevent economic activity from flourishing...Cumbersome red tape holds back more than individual businesses or investors: an economy’s ability to grow sustainably may suffer. Economic freedom to do business goes hand in hand with economic development and a thriving private sector, and these in turn underpin poverty elimination and the pursuit of shared prosperity.”

The notion of reforms seems to assume that there is a clearly signposted, empirically well-tested and, indeed, *singular* path to integration into the global economy and that the interactions of the many moving parts that constitute this process have been boiled down to a hard science, but as the historical literature clearly demonstrates, this is neither an accurate description of how this process panned out in the global North nor has it been a very good predictor of economic

²⁵ This includes starting a business, employing workers, dealing with construction permits, getting electricity, registering property, getting credit, protecting minority investors, paying taxes, trading across borders, contracting with the government, enforcing contracts and resolving insolvency.

²⁶See <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2019/10/24/doing-business-2020-sustaining-the-pace-of-reforms>.

performance in the global South. Indeed, it has performed even worse as a recipe for economic growth and development.

Ironically, the capacity of emerging economies to partake of the spoils of capitalism has, broadly, been inversely proportional to the deference that they have shown to the dictates of global financial institutions. The “lost decade” of the 1980s in Latin America is, in many quarters, directly attributed to the influence of the deregulatory zeal of the “Chicago boys”²⁷, and Africa has ended up, to borrow Collier’s phrase, home to the “Bottom Billion” in significant part because of weak States resulting from Dutch Disease or the Natural Resource Curse²⁸. By contrast, it is fairly unambiguous that the economies of Asia have benefited most from the current era of globalization—and flourished, in large part, by flouting the advice of the economics orthodoxy. In the case of the two fastest growing economies globally—China and India—the State was front and center in the transition of the economies to global capitalism. The Chinese transition from communism to “market socialism” or “state capitalism” was completely State-led, and the product of innovative policies like the iconic Town and Village Enterprises (TVEs) that found ways of connecting State-ownership with individual incentives—by, for instance, separating “ownership rights” from “use rights”.²⁹ In the Indian case, the economy was not even liberalized till 1991—forty-four years after Independence—and its current growth rates are as much the product, for instance, of investments in tertiary education in technology, vestiges of the decidedly closed economy of the Nehruvian-era, as the capacity to partake of the opportunities of global markets in the wake of opening the economy up. Even the more “market-oriented” Modi regime of the last six years or so displays a greatly more complex relationship between government and private enterprise than caricatured by the Washington Consensus approach.³⁰ Indeed, the ongoing centrality of the State in the economies of both countries is amply evident. China and India also illustrate the importance of trust, community and the informal sector in the functioning of economic systems, in the vein of Ostrom’s work on

²⁷ See, for instance, R.H. Bates, J. Coatsworth and J.G. Williamson (2006), *Lost Decades: Lessons from Post-Independence Latin America for Today’s Africa*, London: Center for Economic Policy Research.

²⁸ P. Collier (2008), *The Bottom Billion: Why the Poorest Countries Are Failing and What Can Be Done About It*, Oxford University Press: Oxford.

²⁹ See, on this phenomenon amongst others, C. Wong (1988), “Interpreting Rural Industrial Growth in China”, *Modern China*, p. 3-30.

³⁰ The appropriate economic policy for India has been the subject of heated debate between, for instance, Sen and Bhagwati, see, J. Bhagwati and A. Panagariya (2014): *India’s Tryst with Destiny*, Noida: Collins Business and J. Dreze and A. K. Sen (2013): *An Uncertain Glory*, London: Allen Lane.

the commons: *guanxi* has been key in the Chinese case³¹ and India's famed *jugaad* economy is a central fount of innovation³².

The unfolding transition to capitalism playing out in many parts of the developing world allows us to study the metaphorical entrails of the capitalist system before the wounds are stitched up, as they have been in most of the developed world, nothing could be more useful in providing key clues on the origins of the scars of Western capitalism or, indeed, its health going forward. Instead of this, however, the paradigm of development that has existed for over seventy years ignores not only the correctives to the “narratives of the North” posed by the historical literature but also the empirical evidence on the attributes that account for the relative performance of the nations of the global South. This ahistorical, unempirical approach is not, however, limited to development theory alone—it permeates the dominant paradigm of economics itself.

From Post-colonialism to Post-capitalism?

In the last ten years, as economic historian Skidelsky has pointed out, the “lost decade” has relocated to the most unlikely of regions—the advanced industrial West.³³ Many problems that were considered the exclusive preserve of development theory, or safely in the past—declining growth, rampant inequality, failing institutions, a fractured political consensus, corruption, mass protests and poverty—started to be experienced on Western soil. The watershed moment was the Great Recession starting 2008: crashed stock markets, bankruptcies, foreclosures and evictions not witnessed since the era of the Great Depression, and a bailout package that comprehensively defied the wisdom of the Washington Consensus. Then came the Eurozone Crisis starting in 2009, resulting in the treatment of many European economies (often derisively desecrated as the “PIIGS nations”— to signify Portugal, Ireland, Italy, Greece and Spain) in a fashion that, since the World Wars, had been reserved for nations of the global South. In the year 2016, the spatial and temporal silos were further collapsed by populism coming home to roost at the very heart of the Anglo-American world, starting with the shock Brexit vote and then the Trump election. Economic strife was no longer a matter of other continents or even countries, but as close to “home” as Rustbelt America or Northern England. Suddenly the narratives that were comfortably to do with the *then* and *there* of development and history have

³¹ See A. Haldar and J.E. Stiglitz, “Analyzing Legal Formality and Informality” in D. Kennedy and J.E. Stiglitz (2013): *Law and Economics with Chinese Characteristics*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.

³² N. Radjou, J. Prabhu and S. Ahuja (2012), *Jugaad Innovation: Think Frugal, Be Flexible, Generate Breakthrough Growth*, San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.

³³ R. Skidelsky (2018), “The Advanced Economies Lost Decade”, *Project Syndicate*, April 13.

become, for the Western world, a matter of the *here* and *now*—opening up gashes that had, so far, been proudly sported as war wounds.

To the extent that the global North is in uncharted waters in facing empirical challenges that are novel in the region, at least since the World Wars, it finds itself on the edge of the exhaustion of the current neoclassical economic paradigm. In doing so, the wealth of data provided by the past and the experience of non-Western regions may be the richest source of empirical evidence available to it. The present moment calls for a new canon on capitalism that ends the monopoly of WEIRD societies over theory, and blurs the bright red line separating the “us” from the “them” in the ordaining system of epistemic apartheid that has exiled the global South to area or subaltern studies departments and driven economic history outside the main economics curriculum. As the legal scholar de Sousa Santos argues, what is key at the present moment is the development of “grounded theory” that is a blend of experience and imagination and an epistemology richly informed by empirics.³⁴

In forging the way forward, rather than try to trace a singular locus of the path to global capitalism, it is more fruitful to think in terms of what the more diverse taxonomy of the literature in political science – for instance, Hall and Soskice’s work on the “varieties of capitalism” – going beyond capitalism as a monolithic and underscoring the range of institutional arrangements (from the Scandinavian welfare State to the “free markets” of the U.S.) that can be classed as broadly capitalistic.³⁵ In these accounts, capitalism transcends simplistic binaries to become, instead, a complex and fraught space for institutional contestation between the intersecting entities that are market, State and society.

This insight might help in the process of reverse-engineering what Mazzucato refers to as “the entrepreneurial state” that sees the State as not merely creating the “conditions” that enable innovation, but acting as a *leader* in the process (identifying high growth areas, funding the most uncertain phases of research etc.) and a creator of the knowledge economy precisely because, unlike the private sector, it can focus on domains that are uncertain and risky.³⁶ Her scholarship stresses the role of the National Science Foundation or National Institute of Health in the US, the Medical Research Council in the UK or the Small Business Innovation Research Program and the centrality of the State in the development of computers, the internet, pharma-biotech

³⁴ B.V. De Sousa Santos (2002): *Toward a New Legal Common Sense*, London: Butterworths, p. xviii.

³⁵ P. Hall & D. Soskice (eds.) (2001): *Varieties of Capitalism*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.

³⁶ M. Mazzucato (2013), *The Entrepreneurial State: Debunking Public vs. Private Sector Myths*, Anthem Press: London.

and nanotech. Notably, this process has been very much at play in the case of the development of Artificial Intelligence.

A type of alliance has existed between the historical and the developmental in the context of institutions in the form of the now largely-marginalized law and development movement³⁷, but the current crisis of capitalism presents an opportunity for a truly dynamic role for the forging of an epistemic link between historical and developmental scholarship with a genuine claim to changing the paradigm. The economics orthodoxy marginalizes the assertions of the history of capitalism literature on the basis that they are not *per se* testable in the current period, while mainstream economics ringfences itself from the lessons of development by treating the experiences of the global South as a type of geographical quirk. It is, thus, only a compounded critique based on the insights of both history and development that can act as an effective refutation to the orthodox economics perspective, i.e., by treating development as, in a sense, the future of the history of capitalism.

Conclusion

The current crisis in global capitalism caused by the rise in inequality in the global North, shifts in global power balances, the aftermath of the financial crisis, the looming effects of technological change and the specter of the climate crisis pose a significant challenge to the neoclassical paradigm in economics. In another strain of my work, I stress the importance of mainstreaming the cognitive revolution for economics, but equally, if not more important, is context.³⁸ Core economic concepts—from the significance of institutions like property to contracts³⁹ to, even, as Sen’s capabilities approach illustrates, the meaning of a simple object like a bicycle⁴⁰—are fundamentally shaped by historical trajectory, geographical location and a range

³⁷ See D. Trubek and M. Galanter (1974): “Scholars in Self-Estrangement: Some Reflections on the Crisis in Law and Development Studies in the United States,” *Wisconsin Law Review*, pp. 1062 and A. Haldar (2014), “Law and Development in Crisis: An Empirical Challenge to Current Theoretical Frames”, *Northern Ireland Legal Quarterly* 65 (3).

³⁸ See A. Haldar and J.E. Stiglitz (2016) “Group Lending, Joint Liability and Social Capital”, *Politics and Society* 44 (4), p. 457-497 and A. Haldar (2018), “The Inner Logic of Institutional Evolution: Toward a Theory of the Relationship Between Formal and Informal Law” in M. Guzman (ed.), *Toward a Just Society: Joseph Stiglitz and Twenty-First Century Economics*, New York: Columbia University Press.

³⁹ See A. Haldar and J.E. Stiglitz, “Analyzing Legal Formality and Informality” in D. Kennedy and J.E. Stiglitz (2013): *Law and Economics with Chinese Characteristics*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.

⁴⁰ As Sen stresses the act of a person possessing a bicycle is neither here nor there: what we would typically be concerned with in thinking about the bicycle is whether it provides the “capability of mobility” but in order to do so several contextual preconditions must exist (e.g., the potential cyclist must have both the strength and the skills to cycle or even legs in the first place, and there must also be roads on which the cycle can be used). Equally, one

of other specific factors.⁴¹ The magnitude of this shift for economics in general, and capitalism in particular, would be no less monumental than the inversion of the false certainties of Newtonian physics.

The nature and magnitude of the empirical challenges that the globe, and indeed, the global North confront require the diversity of experience that come from across time periods and a variety of geographical settings. The experience of WEIRD societies may—rather than the paradigmatic norm that most of Western scholarship has posited it as—actually be aberrant and treating a wider range of sources as legitimate founts of epistemic wisdom may hold hope for discovering or imagining alternative futures of our economic systems. Indeed, there may continue to be very good reason to study—and emulate—aspects of the current Western paradigm of global capitalism but the global system can only be brought back from the precipice of crisis by incorporating the lessons of “now” and “then”.

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might add that a cognitive predisposition to use the bicycle must exist: in many societies a woman riding a bicycle may be frowned upon. See further, A.K. Sen (2001): *Development as Freedom*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.

⁴¹ See also A. Haldar (2018), “Thought the 2008 Financial Crisis was Bad? At this Rate there’s Worse to Come” in *The Independent*, August 24 (https://www.independent.co.uk/news/long_reads/financial-crash-2008-economic-crisis-industrial-revolution-big-tech-globalisation-a8504231.html).